

Removal of Nitrous Oxides from Flue Gas – at the Forefront of Legislation

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ABSTRACT

Flue gas emissions have had a major impact on our environment, both as greenhouse gasses and due to their contribution to acid rain. In 1987, major Danish heat and power plants emitted 163.000 tons of SO₂ and 129.000 tons of NO_x gasses. In 2008 these numbers were 5.000 tons of SO₂ and 20.000 tons of NO_x. The abatement of acidic flue gasses has taken a leap forward, but NO_x is lacking behind.

Removal of NO_x gasses is largely performed by state-of-the-art selective catalytic reduction (SCR) catalysis, where NO and NO₂ are reduced to N₂ by use of NH₃. This method has proved highly useful and robust towards other components of flue gas, but a major byproduct is formation of N₂O either from incomplete reduction of NO (at low temperature) or direct oxidation of NH₃ (at high temperature). Our current legislation concentrates on the abatement of NO and NO₂ gasses, but not of N₂O abatement, probably because there has not yet been developed a sufficiently effective and robust method for this reaction. N₂O is also a potent greenhouse gas and it catalyzes the removal of ozone from the atmosphere. We believe that there can be only one reason for lack of legislation on the emission of this gas, namely lack of a suitable catalyst for its decomposition into N₂ and O₂.

In this course, I have studied a number of new and promising catalysts for the SCR reaction as well as for N₂O decomposition by several common characterization techniques in order to assess the composition of their active sites. This will allow us to propose correlations between loading of active material and catalytic activity for catalytically active metal nanoparticles, as well as analyze the size and composition of the active metal sites on the catalyst. By providing an efficient N₂O catalyst, it is our hope that further reduction of greenhouse gasses may be possible.

Denmark has for many years been a forerunner of environmental legislation which has inspired solutions that also have international commercial perspectives. This process is no different, and an efficient N₂O decomposition catalyst has great potential in a tandem SCR-deN₂O process for complete removal of nitrous oxides from flue gas, lessening emissions for the benefit of our environment.